

RESTROSPECTIVE EVALUATIVE ANALYSIS OF APC *O TO GE* CAMPAIGN SLOGAN DURING 2019 ELECTION IN KWARA STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Campaign slogan is considered as one of the means through which a political party or political aspirant gets the approval and votes of electorate in a particular state or nation. Persuading people to vote for a candidate is vital in the political process and critical to the victory of any election. This study, Retrospective evaluative analysis of APC's *ó tó gé* campaign slogan during 2019 election in Kwara State investigates the degree of the influence of the *o to ge* campaign slogan on Kwara State electorate on their choice of candidate in the election. The researcher reviews relevant literature and mass communication theories in order to provide theoretical background for the study. Survey research method was applied and questionnaire was used as the data collection instrument. Multistage and available sampling techniques were adopted and three hundred and eighty-four (384) copies of questionnaire were distributed in six randomly selected local government areas of Kwara State. However, three hundred and seventy-five (375) copies of the questionnaire were returned which represents the 97.7% that was analysed. The outcome depicted that majority (79%) of the respondents were of the opinion that *ó tó gé* campaign slogan contributed immensely to the emergence of APC in Kwara State during the 2019 election. The researcher recommends that politicians and political parties should ensure that credible messages are employed in their campaigns and slogans. This is because most of the electorate are influenced in their choice of candidate when they believe a campaign message to be true. Also, politicians and political parties should ensure that professional personnel make up their creative team in order to come up with apt and pungent campaign slogans.

Keywords: Advertising, campaign slogan, political party, election, electorate

Word count: 268

INTRODUCTON

Campaign slogan is a short and captivating phrase or sentence used by a political party or political aspirant to get the approval and votes of electorate in a particular state or nation. Persuading people to vote for a candidate is vital in the political process as it is the art of what is possible; politics often shares a vocabulary with military activity, and this is specially the case with elections: both winning elections and winning wars involve running successful campaigns (Adrian 2000, p.69).

Words, phrases, other parts of speech, and photos, are main components of slogans, and may have different connotations to effectively arrive at the persuasive-central purpose. In most ways, parties use the techniques of selling a product to sell themselves to voters. Texts as political billboards enjoy certain elements to be successful. For example, they must catch people's attention and "hold it long enough for the message to be taken in". This means that they must be visually eye-catching and must be brief to easily read, as they are often placed strategically along busy roads. The length of the verbal text is deemed to be limited (Adrian 2000, p.63), but its impact, if phrased deeply and thoroughly is tremendous. Therefore, as a way of advertising, it is important that the slogan seeks a discourse that engages the audience and attracts their attention to persuade them with its message (Fuertes-Olivera, Velasco-Sacristán, Arribas-Baño et al 2001, p.1291-1307).

BusinessDictionary.com (2019), defines advertising campaign as a coordinated series of linked advertisements with a single idea or theme which is typically broadcast through several media channels and directed at a particular segment of the population. On the other hand, advertising campaign in politics is the dissemination of tailored messages through the media to influence a political debate, and ultimately, voters. Media campaigns have been a norm for political parties to mobilize and inform electorate on voting political candidate of their choice.

The ó tó gé campaign slogan came for the people of Kwara State at the right time when they really needed a change from the perceived monopolised government. The short but punchy three letter words gained the attention of its target audience and the message intended was understood by them. The ultimate aim of adopting the ó tó gé campaign slogan was also achieved, and that cumulated in winning the election in the state as a way of uprooting the perceived Saraki dynasty. According to the Premium Times, Mr. Saraki is the son of Olusola Saraki, a second republic influential politician and lawmaker. He died in 2012, about a year after he lost a major political battle to his son, Bukola in 2011. Upon serving two terms as governor between 2003 and 2011, Mr. Saraki (Bukola), threw his weight behind Mr. Ahmed of the PDP, contrary to his father's wish to have him replaced with his sister, Gbemisola Saraki. The younger Bukola came out victorious as Mr. Ahmed emerged winner of that deeply rancorous gubernatorial election. Since the death of the older Saraki, Mr. Bukola Saraki has become the new face of the Saraki dynasty."

Saraki's political dynasty which has ruled Kwara State, North Central of Nigeria for 40 years was broken in 2019 general elections which were held on 23rd February, 2019. Independent National Electoral Commission (2019), reveals that, in the governorship election, AbdulRahman Abdulrasaq, the APC's candidate polled 331,546 votes to defeat the runner-up, Razak Atunwa (candidate of PDP-Saraki's party) who polled 114,754 votes. In the election, People's Democratic Party (PDP) unprecedentedly lost the presidential election and the entire three Senatorial and six House of Representatives seats to the APC. According to Agency Report (2019), the major upset was the defeat of the Bukola Saraki in his stronghold, Kwara Central Senatorial zone, by the APC candidate, Ibrahim Oloriegbe.

Prior to the propagation of ó tó gé campaign slogan, there were movements in and out of the two main political parties (APC- All Progressive Congress and PDP- People's Democratic Party). The former Senate President, Dr. Bukola Saraki and his loyalists defected from APC to PDP and this resulted in the major movement of members between the two parties. At this time,

several movements occurred between both parties as their loyalists also defected till the members of each party have been defined. In view of this development, the opposition party (PDP) also came up with its own mantra called o tunya, meaning "let's do it again", in defence. This mantra, however, was not enough for PDP to emerge in any position in the state.

According to *The Guardian Newspapers* (2019), the ó tó gé campaign slogan was conceived and executed by a Lagos Agency. It states that the agency which is named The Hook Creative Agency is a partnership of four young musketeers: Akinwale Muse who functions as Director, Business Development & Strategy while the trio of Toheeb Balogun, Sam Ochonma, and Adebayo Owoshina operate as Creative Directors. It was premised on the knowledge that election cannot be won on campaign of calumny, lousy talks, and name-calling; neither do these unseat a sitting president or any other elected official for that matter. The campaign was also premised on the basis that the last 34 years has been unsavoury with one family deciding the fate of all. This yielded, 'we want this no more, enough is enough.' To achieve optimal effect and secure immediate buy-in by the vast rural community, the communication consultants distilled 'Enough is Enough' into Yoruba language, thus ó tó gé was born, a shorter, sharper, more direct and impactful slang that sits beautifully with the people and addressed the person of the usurper, his class and the issue at hand. There were also other political, religious and social influencers who supported the message the slogan was passing and they played key roles in disseminating the message. For example, Mr. Ibrahim Labaika, a popular Islamic artist released a song titled Ó tó gé (he popularized the slogan through this track), Lai Mohammed and Asiwaju Tinubu among others adopted the slogan.

Overtime, political era witnessed the use of diverse campaign slogans emanating from different political parties to woo the electorate to support their flag bearers at different levels, where elections are expected to hold. The governorship election, that took place in some states of Nigeria especially in 2019, in Kwara State, was not an exception to the above analogy.

There is no doubt that a party through its political slogan can endear itself to the electorate or otherwise. The effect of such slogans on the choice of electorate during the election calls for greater attention among political and communication scholars. The emergence and spread of "ó tó gé" a campaign slogan adopted by the All Progressives Congress, APC, that went viral not among the people of Kwara alone but across the nation, needs to be evaluated to ascertain its influence on the success of the party during the election. It is in the light of the above that this study investigates the influence of the election slogan on the emergence of the candidate of the APC in the last governorship election held in Kwara State.

of APC in the election.

Research Questions

1. To what degree was the Kwara State electorate exposed to the ó tó g campaign slogan?
2. To what extent did ó tó gé campaign slogan influenced Kwara state electorate on their choice of candidate?
3. What is the viewpoint of Kwara State electorate towards ó tó gé campaign slogan?
4. To what extent did ó tó gé campaign slogan contribute to the victory of APC in the election?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Advertising Campaign

Advertising Association of the United Kingdom (2012) defines Advertising as a means of communication with the user of a product or service. Advertising are messages paid by those who send them and are intended to inform or influence people who receive them.

Wikipedia elucidates that Advertising is a marketing communication that employs an openly sponsored, non-personal message to promote or sell a product, service or idea. From this it follows that advertising is usually a non-personalised form of communication, paid by an

identified sponsor, implemented in a certain way through the media and other legal means and aimed to familiarize with some products and its further acquisition by possible large audience. Also, the Federal Law of the Russian Federation (2006) explains that advertising is distributed in anyway, in any form or by any means, addressed to an uncertain number of people aimed at attracting attention to the subject of advertising, the establishment or maintenance of interest in it and its promotion on market. Frovola (2014) directly links advertising to politics. He maintains that advertising determines not only the purchase of maggi, but also the choice of political candidate and in the end determines the path of political development of the country and the politics itself.

Evans and Berman (1995) defines advertising campaign as the set of promotional activities, developed in accordance with the marketing programme and aimed at consumers, representing appropriate market segments, in order to cause their reaction and find a solution for the strategic or tactical objectives of a company.

Advertising campaign is one of the strategies adopted by advertising agencies in order to create awareness and influence the decision of target audience. To Cyberclick (2019), advertising campaign is a specifically designed strategy that is carried across different media in order to both achieve results and to increase brand awareness, sales communication within a specific market. In terms of politics, our market is the electorate of a particular geographical location. Advertising has overtime proved to be the most important marketing tool for organisations to create awareness about their products in the markets. The political sector has adopted this idea by placing their chosen candidate as the product and has come up with various strategies to create awareness and ultimately influence the voting decisions of the target audience. It is noteworthy that the basis of advertising campaign is research. Advertising campaign does not just start when it is aired in the media or when rally is being held. It starts from the plan and steps taken before anything can be aired or rally is organised. There is need for the campaign manager to make thorough findings about the situations of things and the prospects of the candidate's victory. It is through the thorough research the objectives of the campaign is known. Advertising campaign is not a one-time plan, it is a continuous process till the campaign objectives are fulfilled.

Impact of Advertising Campaign

It is noteworthy that advertising campaign if carried out appropriately will produce the desired result, which most of the time is for the political party to emerge as the winner in a particular election. The impact of an advertising campaign cannot be overemphasized because it also gives the political party a strong stand in the geographical territory. Besides, an effective advertising campaign lives on even after the political party has achieved its aim of coming up with the strategy. For example, the campaign song for the Presidential candidate of the Social Democratic Party (SDP), M.K.O. Abiola brought to light the popular slogan people can still remember till date which is 'SDP, MKO, Kingibe-Action! MKO, Kingibe, SDP-Progress.

Political advertisements enable candidates to transfer, deliver and explain their thoughts and electoral programs to the public through available communication media' (Bon et ai. 2012). Commercial advertisements are considered an indirect and impersonal activity that aims to make the targeted population aware of the subject of the advertised issue and convince them to choose it (Shah, 2016). From another point of view, political advertisements target to define, inform and tell electors (voters) about electoral candidates and work to urge and convince them to elect electoral candidate by concentrating on presenting candidates' positive characteristics and advantages compared with other candidates, and explain their electoral programs (Steenburg, 2015).

Political Campaign

Chile (2011) reveals that campaign refers to systematic efforts in coordinating all relevant activities over a long period of time to obtain a specific and all-encompassing objective.

Further, Aduradola and Ojukwu (2013, p.106) explain that political campaign is the mobilization of forces either by an organization or individual to influence others in order to effect an identified and desired political change. It shows people and particularly, political candidates' ability to sensitize the political community in relation to making the community see them as potentials and better representatives of the people. Supporting this view Ezegwu, Enem and Ndife (2017, p.53) stress that political campaign is an organized effort which is to influence the decision-making process within a specific group or people. Sustaining the fact that political campaign is not an haphazard action.

Ginsberg (2009) cited in Olujide, Adeyemi and Gbadeyan (2011, p.180) sees political campaign as organized effort by a political party or candidate for public office to attract the support of voters in an election. Asemah, Nwamuo and Edegoh (2004) submit in their definition that political campaign always seek to influence the decision of the populace in supporting the subject of the campaign, when they say that a political campaign is an organized effort which seeks to influence the decision making process within a specific group. In political or electoral campaigns, representatives are chosen or referendums decided. In modern politics, the highest profile political campaigns are focused on candidates for the position of the Head of State or Head of Government, usually a President or Prime minister. From the forgoing it is apt to submit that political campaign is a systematic and planned bid which tilts towards enhancing the decision-making process within a particular cluster.

Ginsberg (2009) cited in Olujide, Adeyemi and Gbadeyan (2011, p.180) is of the view that political campaign includes five basic elements; professional public relations, polling, broadcast media, direct mail and internet. In democracies, political campaign refers to electoral campaigns, wherein representatives of particular states are chosen. Also, Pistekova (2008) as cited in Olujide et al., (2011) believes that for any political campaign to be effective it must be made up of three main elements; message, money, and machine. The message is the statement and it is one of the most important features of a political campaign. The campaign messages often contain the issues that candidate intend to share with the electorate. The messages which often centre on policy issues, summarizes the main ideas of the campaign and are often repeated to create a lasting impression in the minds of the voters. For example, it is during political campaigns/ rallies that candidates project their campaign messages to the electorate who digest and filter their manifestos to understand whether or not their ambitions are realistic. Often times, political actors utilize pernicious propaganda during political campaigns. They make promises that they cannot keep over the years and it has become a recycling or recurrent decimal. It appears some electorates are beginning to understand their sneaking pattern and are reacting accordingly.

Pistekova (2008) further concludes that hundreds of thousand dollars was spent on opinion polls to find out what is the right message to win the elections. Other important features of a successful campaign are machine, the human capital and the people who are loyal to the cause and help the candidate. This crowd of people usually requires managers that make the tactical decisions and manage the volunteers. The last important element of a political campaign is money. The candidate organizes meetings involving large donors and sends emails to small donors just to raise the money for the campaign because the costs are enormous.

Political Advertisement

The political advertisement is considered a comparative form of advertising that focuses, directly and obviously, on candidate's positive issues and/or on the negative issues of other candidates (Yousif and Alsamydai, 2012). Electors are aware of the importance of investigating information published and broadcast by opposing candidates in order to carry out an appropriate election and that they must take responsibility for their election and be wary, cautious and note the guardianship nature of the election process. This is primarily because there are potential risks and threats when the wrong election result is obtained, and there can

be dangerous consequences with respect to social, political and economic aspects (Al Sari and Al Aloosi, 2013).

Political advertisements on Television have become the foremost means of communication by parties to persuade ambivalent voters, and to ensure that they turn up and vote for their side on election day. A significant turnover or unexpected shift in votes on election day ultimately ensures the success of advertising (Mamood, 2000). Those who work in advertising focus on designing advertising messages and selecting appropriate methods to reach targeted voters. In fact, advertisement campaigns for electoral candidates are organized processes that aim to impact decision-making, including electing the candidate. This process includes a series of advertisement campaigns through available communication methods or media such as social media, short messages, newspapers, Television, radio circulation and broadcasting, printed advertising and public seminars (Yousif and Alsamydai, 2012). All these activities are processed to circulate and spread information about the candidate concerning their educational qualifications, past experiences and electoral program, in order to form a positive mental image about the electoral candidate among voters in order to motivate the voters to vote for them (Alsamydai et al, 2012).

Advertisement campaigns for electoral candidates aim to distinguish electoral candidates and work to show their good characters and explain their electoral program on a very wide range of issues, in order to gain support of those who agree with the candidate and their electoral program. Such campaigns also aim to create a good impression and urge the electorate to choose a particular candidate by spreading materials in available media and arranging seminars and festival galas (Alsamydai and Al Khasawneh, 2013).

Crispus (2015) noted that extensive use of mass media as an effective communication tool is evident during political campaigns worldwide. It stands out as a political mobilization medium in many countries. Its coverage, diversity and change within the social context have made mass media social mobilization tool. Television, radio, newspapers, and posters are among different forms of mass media used for political mobilization during elections.

Kotler and Armstrong (2013) indicate that marketing is highly suitable, in this context because marketing commodities, services, individuals, organizations, places and others is highly effective. Thus, politicians rely on marketers' skills in marketing themselves through advertisement campaigns and by determining people's needs, personal characters and the electoral program that meets those needs and promotes the candidate as well.

The trio of Olujide et al., (2011) explained that the past two decades have witnessed the increased use of political advertising in Nigeria. Prior to this period, political rallies, personal contact and speeches have been popularly used for mobilizing electorate' support for elections (Chiang and Park 1998; Beard 2000; Opebi, 2004). This probably might be as a result of development in information technology and the realization of the potent force of media communication in packaging not only products but ideas. However, in Nigeria, smear campaigns against political opponents started a long time ago. This is most especially by the dominant political party against opposition parties. Electoral campaigns are marketing actions employed to get votes in election. It enables parties and their candidates know how to allocate their resources and develop better knowledge about how and why voters make their choices (Apospori et al. 2010). However, most of these political adverts and campaign are negative advertising. According to Opeibi (2004), the use of negative adverts is due to several reasons amongst which include: fear of losing election, paucity of ideas and probably to settle old scores between perceived political "enemies". For example, during the Second Republic, in Kwara State the dominant party, National Party of Nigeria (NPN) in trying to tell the opposition that their candidate is popular sang this song:

Saraki mi gboro titi, o mi gboro. Oloye mi gboro titi, o mi gboro. This means Saraki (NPN financier and strong man) is shaking the city, he is shaking the city. The chief is shaking the

city, he is shaking the city. The opposition party, The Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN), counter with this song: Ile won na nu ni (x2ce) Ile abere wo bi ile ekute, Ile won na nu ni. This song literally means: This is their house (x2ce). Their house like the rat's house (You have to bend down to enter). This is their house. This song was trying to discredit the National Party of Nigeria's members as poor not only of material well-being but of ideas. In 2003, the supporters of All Nigerian People's Party (ANPP) in trying to defy the opposition party leaders coined this party slogan: Up Lawal! No Shaking! Second term! Continuity forever!!!! The People's Democratic Party (the opposition Party) replied with this Slogan: Poku Lawal (Poku Lawal is an adulterated form of Up Lawal); Bukola for Governor. This means unimportant Lawal; Bukola for Governor.

The political advert wars in the media were also popular in the Fourth Republic. In Lagos State, we have the political advert war between Alliance for Democracy (AD) and the Progressive Action Congress (PAC). Alliance for Democracy informed the electorate that the opposition party, the Progressive Alliance Congress, wants to finish Lagos and the electorate should not "agree". The Progressive Alliance Congress replied with "Let's do what?" and urged the electorate to vote for their party and candidates. There was a similar scenario in Kwara State between All Nigerian's People Party (ANPP) and the opposition party, People's Democratic Party (PDP). The Advert for All Nigerian People's Party urged the electorate not to "serve the son" because they have "served the father". The People's Democratic Party gave its own bombshell by reminding the electorate of failed promised by the All Nigerian People's Party. One important thing about political advertising is that it is interesting and sometimes offers the electorate reliable information about the candidates. Nigerian electorate are now being exposed more to political adverts than ever before and this has consequently made them to be conscious about the kind of political decisions they would want to make in the choice of their candidates for elective post.

Ojekwe (2015) in her research work noted that in Nigeria, political advertising has grown immensely in the past two decades. This is as a result of the recent awareness by political parties and their candidates on the usefulness of advertising in making the electorate better aware of the candidates as a better brand and in communicating their offerings in form of manifestoes to these same electorate. Olujide et al., (2010) as cited in Ojekwe, G., (2015) explained that, advertising have become the most commonly used technique to create a favourable image for the candidate and a negative image for the opponent. Before now, political parties and candidates channeled most of their resources into political rallies, speeches and direct contact to gather the support of electorate, as noted by Opeibi (2004). Between the 2007, 2011 and most recent 2023 elections in Nigeria; presidential and gubernatorial, the use of political advert campaigns have widened from mode of delivery, type of language used, to forms of media used to communicate these messages.

The 2007 gubernatorial election in Lagos state witnessed the flood of both traditional and new media with media campaigns of the three strong contenders who were; Babatunde Fashola of Alliance for Democracy (AD), Musuliu Obanikoro of People's Democratic Party (PDP) and a fresh face, Jimi Agbaje of Accord.

Because of the popularity of these three candidates amongst the electorate, campaigns became highly competitive. Each candidate tried to outdo the other using political advert campaigns. They came up with various jingles such as: everybody loves Jimi Agbaje and slogans like ".... *Ekoonibaje o*" amongst others. Also, Nworah (2011) as cited in Ojekwe (2015) said the 2011 presidential election between former president Goodluck Ebele Jonathan of the PDP and General Muhammad Buhari of the Congress for Progressive Change (CPC) had its peculiarities. In the sense that, Since Goodluck Ebele Jonathan had not been elected president during his first term, he was saddled with the responsibility of convincing the electorate that he was a better choice than his strongest opponent. This he did by investing a lot of funds into

media campaigns which included traditional media and the new media. In 2023 presidential election, the *Emilokan* political slogan made waves in Nigerian's media space. Essentially, *Emilokan*, which translates to "it is my turn" in English was popularized by Bola Tinubu, the then presidential candidate of the All Progressives Congress (APC). The slogan was initially used during the APC primary election and was meant to convey Tinubu's conviction that it was his turn to lead Nigeria. Interestingly, *Emilokan* started as an expression of anger, but eventually became a catchy slogan that has been used in various contexts, including memes and comedy skits. Some analysts believed that the slogan has helped to shift public perception in Tinubu's favour, portraying him as a victim of betrayal and conspiracy. Today, this slogan has become a cultural phenomenon in Nigeria, sparking conversations and debates across the country.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

This study is theoretically anchored on the Agenda Setting Theory developed in 1922 by Walter Lippman when he expressed his concern on the vital role that mass media can do in influencing the setting of certain image on the public mind (Lippmann, 1922, p.9-16). In portraying the influence of mass media, Lippmann gives an example of individuals who supposed to be enemies while their countries are at war. Instead of becoming enemies, without having access to information about the war through media, those individuals are able to live harmoniously in a secluded island. Lippmann indicates on how mass media can set a particular agenda which can influence the opinions of the public. However, he never uses the term "agenda setting theory" in his book. Nevertheless, he did generate the foundation for the agenda setting theory. In the later years, from Lippmann's time the term "agenda setting theory" was popularized.

The agenda setting theory is a theory that discusses on how the mass media influences in making a certain issue as a public agenda. The public agenda is the main focus or prime issue which the members of the society or public concern about. This theory elaborates the connection in term of relationships between the emphasis that the mass media put as an issue and the media audiences or the public's reaction or attributes to such issue (Littlejohn and Foss, 2009). Other researchers suggest that the agenda setting can be set up by politicians and public relations practitioners (Walgrave and Aelst, 2006; McCombs and Shaw, 1993; Roberts and McCombs, 1994). These researches open the possibility of the government's role in promoting their policy through the agenda setting of mass media. This is heavily agreeable when it comes to election periods or political agenda (Walgrave, Soroka and Nuytemans: 2008; Rogers and Dearing: 1988). Scholars. such as Everett Rogers and James Dearing (1988) believed that the agenda setting theory in connection with mass media stands with interrelationships between three agendas. Such agenda are identified as (i) public agenda, (ii) media agenda and (iii) policy agenda. They claim such policy agenda can be developed based on the issues that the governments and other policy makers create. Occasionally, the reality of the world offers a new issue as a setting of agenda in mass media. Such can happened in referring to natural disasters such as earthquake or tsunami or wars. This will equally affect directly or indirectly the above mentioned agenda..

Subsequent studies indicate that the mass media can influence the audience's thinking. Directly or indirectly contribute to the forming of the audience's opinions (Wanta, Golan and Lee: 2004; McCombs and Shaw, 1972; McCombs and Shaw, 1997). From such discussions, the scholars extend the scope of the agenda setting to the cognitive aspects of the agenda setting function such as the structuring of the agenda by the mass media and the influences on how the audiences consider or feel on the agenda (Scheufele, 2000; Scheufele and Tewksbury, 2007).; In other words, the media was able to influence the audience's opinion through the way in which the campaign was carried out and the consistency in disseminating it to the public. It's a different thing to have a good campaign slogan and it is another issue entirely to be able to manipulate the media to achieve campaign objectives. The media raise the slogan of ó tó gé to

public parlance of discourse and it becomes a public debate and a day to day term during the election period.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research adopted the descriptive design of the survey type. This enabled the researcher to gather information from the respondents on the role of ó tó campaign slogan during the 2019 election in the state.

The population consisted of all eligible electorate in Kwara State. According to Pulse.ng, the number of registered voters for the 2019 election in Kwara State was 1,406,457. Therefore, the study population for this research work is 1,406,457.

According to Wimmer and Dominick Sample Size calculator, the sample size for this study was three hundred and eighty-four (384). The calculator assured an error of no more than five percent at 95 percent confidence level. This sample size was picked from the selected six local governments of Kwara State. Sixty-four (64) respondents were selected in each of the six local governments.

Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw samples. The first stage was to establish a sample frame for the sixteen local governments from Kwara State, of which a selection of six LGAs was made through the use of the simple random sampling technique. Four wards were randomly selected from each of the LGA resulting to a total of 24 wards from the six LGAs. Afterwards, five streets were selected from each ward using simple random sampling. It is noteworthy that the researcher randomly selected the streets evenly by skipping the first street and picked the next street, skipped the other street and picked the next one until five streets were selected. 16 respondents were picked per ward. Every respondent for this study was selected on the basis of having been exposed to ó tó gé, participated in the election and being available during the administration of the questionnaire. The choice of these sampling techniques was to ensure a true representation of the entire population of Kwara State.

RESULTS

The analysis on the return rate of the questionnaire distributed to respondents showed that 384 copies of questionnaire were administered to the selected respondents, but a total of 375 copies of questionnaires were retrieved at the point of collection. The percentage of the return rate is 97.7% with a missing percentage of 2.3%

Item 1: How did you first get to know about o to ge campaign logan?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 1” revealed that 108 of the respondent representing 28.8% first heard the slogan from radio, while 73 of the respondents representing 19.5% first heard it from the television, 53 of the respondents representing 14% first heard it from the magazine while 119 representing 31.7% claimed they first heard it from other sources. Other sources mentioned include social media, friends, family members, neighbor, political and social gathering. It was discovered through this study that over sources like the social media, friends, family members, neighbor, political and social gathering different which are different from the traditional media of television, magazine and newspaper has the highest frequency of 119 representing (31.7%) followed by the radio with the frequency of 108(28.8%). This study aligns is thought with the finding of Conway et al (2015) that, in recent times, the potency of social media utilization and adoption, as well as its impact on political campaigns, has attracted an array of prior and recent studies. Although, Chadwick (2017). However, himelboim, et al exchange has introduced a new pathway for inducing political attitudes and participation and enhancing participatory communication, as well as faster dialoguing and engagement. The recent e-campaigning tool, social media such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter according to Oelsner (2015) allow political aspirants to speaks to voters at once in more personalized, responsive and dialogue manner, enhancing the connection between citizens and candidates. In summary, the social media provides the platform for campaign organizers to pass by to

conventional media and communicate directly with voters via websites and other social media sites such as Facebook and Twitter.

Item 2: How often were you exposed to *o to ge* campaign slogan during the election?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 2” revealed that 56 respondents representing 15% of the total respondents get exposed to the slogan every day, 166 respondents representing 44% get exposed to the slogan once in a week and once in a month respectively. This analysis reflects that the electorate repeatedly got exposed to the “*o to ge* slogan” as suggested in Module 6 of the National Democratic Institute (2013) states that same message of a campaign slogan must be repeated at every opportunity, nothing that for a message to register with voters, they have to hear that same message many times in many different ways.

Items 3: Do you agree that all the electorate in Kwara State heard about *o to ge* campaign slogan?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 3” revealed that 50 respondents representing 13% of the total respondents strongly agree that all the electorates in Kwara State heard about *o to ge* campaign slogan. 201 respondent representing 54% agree that all the electorates in Kwara State heard about *o to ge* campaign slogan. 34 respondent representing 9% strongly disagree that all the electorate in Kwara State heard about *o to ge* campaign slogan. 53 respondent representing 14% disagree that all the electorate in Kwara State heard about *o to ge* campaign slogan. 37 respondents representing 10% ticked ‘not sure’ as to whether all electorate got exposed to the *o to ge* campaign slogan. This analysis means that majority of the respondents agree that all electorate got exposed to the slogan.

Item 4: The *o to ge* campaign slogan was the most popular campaign slogan during the last election?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 4” revealed that 312 respondents representing 83% of the total respondents believe that *o to ge* was the most popular political slogan during the last election in Kwara State election.

Research Question Two

This sub-section presents data which addresses the second research question which is to choice of candidate. To answer this question, items 5, 6 and 7 of the questionnaire were used and the data gathered from the respondents are presented below:

Item 5: *o to ge* campaign slogan had influence on your choice of candidate Result from the analysis of data from “item 6” revealed that 301 respondents representing 80% of the total respondents agreed that it is true that the *o to ge* campaign slogan had influence on their choice of candidate.

Item 6: what the respondents like about *o to ge* campaign slogan

Result from the analysis of data from “item 6” revealed that 98 respondents representing 26% of the total respondents liked about the *o to ge* campaign slogan was its captivating nature, 107 respondents representing 29% liked it for being impactful, while 70 respondents representing 45% liked the *o to ge* campaign slogan because it influenced their choice of candidate.

Research Question Three

This sub-section presents data which addresses the third objective of this study which is to know the perception of Kwara state electorate towards *o to ge* campaign. To answer this research question, items 5, 6 and 7 of the questionnaire were used and the results gathered from the respondents are presented below:

Item 7: What is your perception of *o to ge* campaign slogan?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 7” revealed that 57 respondents representing 15% of the total respondents were of the perception that the *o to ge* campaign slogan informed them. 296 respondent representing 79% of the total respondents were of the perception that the *o to ge* campaign slogan persuaded them. 5 respondents representing 1% were of the perception

that the *o to ge* campaign slogan dissuaded them. 17 respondents representing 5% were of the perception that the *o to ge* campaign slogan had no impact .

Item 8: Do you agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan was apt for the political scenario in Kwara State during the last election?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 8” revealed that 269 respondents representing 72% of the total respondents strongly agree that the *o to ge* campaign slogan was apt for the political scenario in Kwara State during the last election. 52 respondents representing 14% agree that the *o to ge* campaign slogan was apt for the political scenario in Kwara State during for the last election. 19 respondents representing 5% strongly disagree that the *o to ge* campaign slogan was apt for the political scenario in Kwara State during the last election . Therefore, this analysis means majority of the respondents strongly agree that the *o to ge* campaign slogan was apt for the political scenario in Kwara State during the last election.

Item 9: To what extent do you agree that the electorate had a good understanding of *oto ge* campaign slogan?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 9” revealed that 304 respondents representing 81% of the total respondents agreed that the electorate had a good understanding of the *o to ge* campaign slogan at a very high extent. 63 respondents representing 17% agreed that the electorate had a good understanding of the *o to ge* campaign slogan at a high extent. 8 respondents representing 2% opined that they had the understanding of the campaign at a low extent

Research Question Four

This sub-section presents data that address the fourth objective of this research work which is to know the extent to which *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed to the victory of APC in the election. To fulfill this objectives, items 10 and 11 of the questionnaire were used and the data gathered from the respondents are presented below:

Item 10: *O to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during the last election in Kwara State?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 10” revealed that 282 respondents representing 75% of the total respondents strongly agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during the last election in Kwara State. 19 respondents representing 5% strongly disagree *o to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during the last election in Kwara State. 15 respondents representing 4% disagree that *o to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during the last election in Kwara State: 4 respondents representing 1% are not sure whether *o to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during the last election in Kwara State. Therefore, this analysis means majority of the respondents (75%) strongly agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for APC during 2019 election.

Item 11: *O to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC in Kwara State during the last election?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 11” revealed that 298 respondents representing 79% of the total respondents strongly agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC in Kwara State during the last election. 49 respondents representing 13% agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC respondents representing 13% agree that *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC in Kwara state during the last election. 15 respondents representing 4% strongly disagree that *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC in Kwara state during the last election. 3 respondent representing 1% are not sure whether *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to emergence of APC in Kwara state during the last election.

Item 12: How would you assess the effectiveness of the *o to ge* campaign slogan during the last election in Kwara state?

Result from the analysis of data from “item 12” revealed that 273 respondents representing 73% of the total respondents gave the assessment that *o to ge* campaign slogan during the last election in Kwara State was very effective. 78 respondents representing 21% gave the verdict that *o to ge* campaign slogan during the last election in Kwara State was effective. 20 respondents representing 5% opined in their assessment that *o to ge* campaign slogan was very effective during the last election in Kwara State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from the study revealed that majority of the respondents were of the opinion that the *o to ge* campaign slogan contributed immensely to the emergence of APC in Kwara State during the last election (in 2019). In the same vein, majority of the respondents noted that the campaign slogan was very effective during the last election in the state. To reinforce this, more than 70% of the respondents strongly agreed that the campaign slogan mobilized more electorate for the election. Generally, apathy of Nigerians toward exercising their voting rights is very pronounced such that it is regarded as unusual when an unexpected number of eligible voters turn up. The research carried out by Olujide, Adeyemi and Gbadeyan (2011) corroborates the findings of this study as they found out that political advertising is having significant effect on the electorate. Also, in the findings of Udeze and Akpan(2013), it is discovered that political advertising aided electorate choice of candidates to the extent that they perceive such messages to be true. In the course of analyzing the respondents’ got to hear *ó tó gé* campaign slogan. From the foregoing, it can be said that agenda setting theory came into play. Agenda setting theory assumes that the media tells the public what to think of and in relation to this discourse, political reality is mostly set by the media. chery an sines arte me foreglin peibe said to that od and in relation to this discourse, political reality is mostly set by the media.

Furthermore, this study revealed that most of the respondents (80%) believe it to be true that the campaign slogan influenced their choice of candidates. This depicts that the purpose for which the campaign slogan was created was achieved. The election result said it all and also, the result of this study has helped in evaluating the campaign slogan as used during the 2019 election in Kwara State.

In response to what the respondents liked about the campaign slogan, it was discovered that most of them liked it for the fact that it influenced their choice of candidate as more than 70% of the total respondents believed that the slogan persuaded them to vote for the political party.

CONCLUSION

From the foregoing, this research therefore concludes that the electorate in Kwara State were very much exposed to *ó tó gé* campaign slogan. This justifies that campaign slogan remains an authentic tool in the victory of any election provided the words are strategically and creatively packaged to persuade potential voters.

The campaign slogan has to a very large extent influenced the choice of candidate of Kwara State electorate. It has also come to the conclusion that there is significant relationship between the campaign slogan and the victory of APC in the election.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study, the researcher recommends that:

1. Politicians and political parties should ensure that credible messages are employed in their campaigns and slogans. This is because most of the electorate are influenced in their choice of candidate when they believe a campaign message to be true.
2. The use of radio in the course of carrying political advertisement should be encouraged. This is because it is considered to be easily accessible and inexpensive to procure.
3. Politician and political parties should ensure that professional personnel make up their creative team in order to come up with apt and pungent campaign slogans. It is noteworthy that most political parties have slogans that represent what their party stands for. However, their attempt to come up with a good campaign slogan that represent what their party stands for. However, their attempt to come up with a good campaign slogan for a particular election is sometimes weak.

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